

BR06 - Investigating the Leaching, Desilication and Precipitation of Aluminium Tri-Hydroxides from a Bauxite Residue-Bauxite By-Product Slag

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Abstract

The ENSUREAL initiative is investigating the revival of the long discontinued Pedersen process for use in processing lower grades and different types of bauxite ores. The Pedersen process is a combined pyro and hydro-metallurgical process that has been proposed as an almost waste free alternative to the Bayer process for production of metallurgical grade alumina. This study evaluated the hydrometallurgical processing of slag which was composed of a mixture of bauxite residue (red mud) and a calcite-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product. The slag contained Al in the form of gehlenite and mayenite. The study investigated the leachability of the slag, the effectiveness of a desilication step and the precipitation of aluminium tri-hydroxides. All three processes were investigated at lab-scale using a 1 L jacketed glass reactor. The results from early tests in this ongoing study have been promising.

Samples of the slag (100 g), ground to $-75\ \mu\text{m}$, were leached using a 1 L solution of 60 g/l Na_2CO_3 at 90°C for 90 mins. As much as 65% of the Al was extracted with an indication that perhaps the amount could increase with longer leaching time. The desilication step was carried out by treating the leachate solution with CaO and mixing for 2 hrs at 70°C . This resulted in a small reduction of the Si content by 27%. The desilicated solution was sparged with a mixture of Ar and CO_2 at a gas flowrate of 1.5 slpm and CO_2 partial pressure of 50%. This was done for 30 mins at a temperature of 25°C . When precipitation commenced the gas flow was stopped. The solution was allowed to age for 3 days at 25°C while agitated at 200 rpm. The resulting precipitate was composed of the aluminium tri-hydroxides bayerite (85%), gibbsite (12%) and nordstrandite (3%).

Keywords: Pedersen process, alumina, leaching, desilication, precipitation.

1. Introduction

A revival of the Pedersen process has been proposed by the ENSUREAL initiative in response to the need for more environmentally friendly and sustainable methods to process low grade bauxite ores. Additionally, the Pedersen process may also be used to process red mud resulting from processing high grade bauxite ores through the Bayer process. The Pedersen process was successfully used during the period 1928-1969 to produce alumina in Høyanger, Norway [1]. It was eventually closed due to the economic strain of less efficient smelter technology [2] and it could not compete with the Bayer process in treating high grade bauxite ores. However, improvement in the smelter technology, the need for more sustainable processes in the mining industry and the need to address the red mud product from the Bayer process have renewed interest in this process. The process potentially addresses all these matters while being an almost zero-waste process producing by-products that can be used in other industries.

The process is a combined pyro and hydrometallurgical process that can be described in three stages [3, 4, 5]. The first is the smelting of the bauxite ore to produce calcium aluminate slags and pig iron as a by-product to feed the cast iron industry. In the second stage the slags are leached with sodium carbonate solutions to dissolve the aluminate minerals and leave behind a mostly calcium carbonate product referred to as grey mud. This by-product may be used in the cement or fertilizer industry. The leach liquor is then sparged with CO₂ gas to precipitate alumina trihydroxide which is dried and calcined to produce metallurgical grade alumina.

The precipitation process is very complex and involves the absorption of CO₂ gas by the sodium aluminate solution (equations 1 and 2) which leads to the neutralization of free hydroxyl ions by H⁺ ions in solution. During this step several physiochemical sub-processes such as mass transfer through the gas-film occur. This step creates a suitable pH for the hydrolysis (decomposition) of aluminate ions and precipitation of fine aluminum hydroxide particles (equation 3) [6, 7, 8].

A part of this study will evaluate the leachability of a slag produced by the smelting-reduction of a mixture of bauxite residue (red mud) and a calcite-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product. The slag contains some SiO₂ hence the effectiveness of a desilication step on the leach solution to reduce Si content in the solution and final product will also be investigated. Finally the precipitation of aluminium tri-hydroxides from the desilicated leach solution will be investigated.

2. Materials and Methods

The procedure for the smelting-reduction process used to prepare the slag is described by Lazou [9]. The starting material for making the slag was 1 kg of a mixture of bauxite residue (red mud) (60%) and a calcite-rich bauxite beneficiation by-product (40%). To this lime (CaO) in a ratio of 21wt% of the mixture was added. The resulting slag was crushed and screened to produce a bulk sample that was <75 μm. The material was then subject to splitting using 2-way rifle splitters and an 8-way Retsch DR rotary splitter to produce sample sizes of 100 g for leaching test work. Smaller sub-samples were obtained for analysis by XRF (Table 1) while XRD analysis (Figure 1) showed the slag contained Al as gehlenite and mayenite. Perovskite and Larnite were also present.

Table 1. Normalized semi-quantitative analysis of slag wt%.

Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	MgO	Fe	SO ₃
39.6	43.9	6.99	5.84	0.17	1.82	0.18
MnO	Na ₂ O	ZrO ₂	SrO	Cr ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅	P ₂ O ₅
0.06	1.19	0.14	0.06	0.03	<0.01	<0.05

2.1 Leaching

A 100 g sample of slag was placed in a jacketed glass reactor and 1 L of solution was added to it. The resulting slurry was heated to 90°C and held at that temperature for 1.5 h. The temperature was controlled by circulating a heated silicon oil through the reactor jacket and a temperature probe was placed in the reactor vessel. The slurry was agitated at a speed of 500 rpm using a stainless-steel overhead stirrer with a paddle impeller. The temperature probe was connected to the agitator which displayed the result in addition to the agitation speed. A glass condenser with

cooling water was attached to the top of the reactor to help maintain the reactor volume. During the experiment samples were withdrawn at 15-minute intervals using a syringe and filtered with a 0.2 µm Millipore vacuum filter to produce clear samples suitable for ICP-MS analysis of Al and Si. At the end of the experiment the slurry was cooled and then vacuum filtered using a büchner funnel and general purpose Whatman filter paper to produce a filter cake for further analysis by XRF and XRD. The filtrate was set aside for the desilication and precipitation steps. All experiments were conducted using 1 L solution of 60 g/L Na₂CO₃ prepared from deionized water and analytical grade Na₂CO₃. Higher solution concentrations produce a leachate solution that precipitates dawsonite instead of the desired aluminium hydroxides [10]. In total two experiments were conducted (Table 2); in the first the filter cake was dried and ground with a pestle and mortar. This was done to help remove the passivation layer that has been reported by Azof et al. [11] which limits the extraction of Al in agitated leaching to 50-60%. The sample was then re-leached with the same solution as before. In the second experiment the sample was leached only once with no mechanical treatment but 6 g of NaOH was added. It is reported that this is needed to limit the dissolution of Si [11, 12] which is a critical contaminant in the final alumina product.

Figure 1. XRD analysis of slag. Minerals were identified using EVA software and quantified using TOPAS software.

Table 2. Leaching tests used 60 g/L Na₂CO₃, 1 L volume of solution and 100 g of slag.

Experiment	1 st Stage Leach	Intermediate step	2 nd Stage Leach
1	90°C, 1.5 h, 500 rpm	Slag is ground with pestle and mortar	Slag is re-leached with solution from 1 st stage leach
2	90°C, 1.5 h, 500 rpm, 6 g NaOH	None	None

Table 9. XRF and PSD analyses of selected contaminants in precipitates vs industrial specification.

	Industrial Spec.	Experiment 1	Experiment 2
CaO	<0.04	0.09	0.20
SiO ₂	<0.015	0.55	0.55
TiO ₂	<0.004	0.00	0.00
Fe ₂ O ₃	<0.015	0.01	0.03
Na ₂ O	<0.4	0.57	3.01
PSD / median size (µm)	50 % > 44 µm	15.97	28.91

4. Conclusion

Early test work has shown that the Pedersen process is a potential route to further explore as an alternative to the Bayer process for processing secondary bauxite materials. All processes involved in the hydrometallurgical section of this process have produced promising results that leave room for further investigation. The leaching has produced extractions of 65% Al and can potentially produce more with longer leach times and higher Na₂CO₃ concentrations in the leach solution. The desilication step has shown it can remove Si by using Ca. Use of higher amounts of CaO may help reduce the Si and Ca further in the solution prior precipitation. The combination of carbonation and aging has shown it can produce the desired Al tri-hydroxide precipitates. Longer carbonation times are likely to result in complete precipitation of the Al from solution.

5. Acknowledgements

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